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Manual Material Handling & Spinal Compression: A Pilot Study

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KEYWORDS

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MMH
Lifting
Lumbar compression
2D

ABSTRACT

Manual materials handling (MMH) is a common cause of low back injury and low back pain (LBP). Low back injury is a major challenge in many industries and consumes the largest portion of the workers' compensation dollar. Low back pain is responsible for more lost workdays and disability than any other musculoskeletal disorder (MSD). Many industries require employees to engage in MMH that cause significant risk to their spinal health. This study investigated the application of two different lifting techniques. Spinal compression was estimated in four subjects lifting a 35 lbs load using two different lifting techniques. Finding revealed average compressive forces between 849 lbs/in² and 1023 lbs/in². Findings reveals a significant reduction (p-value < 0.05) in spinal compression using the Powerlift™ method compared to the traditional squat lift. Findings suggest that different lifting methods may reduce or increase stresses to the back. Investigators advocate for the adoption of Poweflift™ where possible to reduce risk for back injuries.

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

The workers engaged in manual materials handling (MMH) are at higher risk for low back injury and associated pain leading to more lost workdays due to injury more than any other occupational group (Ferguson et al., 2019). Material handlers come in all shapes and sizes and from a variety of different backgrounds and industries. The term “material handler” doesn't necessarily refer to laborers, stocking clerks, or freight handlers, but anyone who handles material by performing the following tasks: Lifting, lowering, pushing, pulling and carrying loads (Rajesh, 2016). Manual laborers perform a higher frequency of similar, and often, more strenuous MMH tasks managing in a wide range of loads (Ferguson et al., 2019). Many workers are at high risk of developing musculoskeletal disorders due to MMH stresses associated with lifting, lowering, pushing, pulling, and carrying loads. For example, manual laborers suffered 15.6% of all musculoskeletal injuries in 2016 (BLS, 2018). MMH-associated lower back pain (LBP) continues to be an immense challenge for employers and safety and health professionals (OSHA, 1994; Tang et al., 2020; Waters et al, 2007).

Each year more than 1 million people in the US suffer from back injuries. The annual incidence of low back pain has been estimated at 7% in the general population (Fatoye, Gebrye & Odeyemi, 2019). In fact, 1 out of every 5 or more workplace injuries is a back injury. Back injuries comprised 38.5% of all musculoskeletal injuries in 2016 (BLS, 2018). Eighty percent of these injuries occurred on the lower

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back and 75% of them happened during lifting activities (BLS, 2018). The most common type of injury workers encounter is strains and/or sprains, which can originate from several different MMH related factors (Marras, 2000; Tang et al., 2020; Water et al., 2007). Back pain is multifactorial may also be related to many other possible factors beyond MMH such as health status, poor posture, physical condition, lifestyle hobbies and activities, poor body mechanics, and psychosocial (Marras, 2000; Tang et al., 2020; Waters et al., 2007).

Low-back pain ranks number one among the most prevalent painful conditions experienced by individuals throughout their lives, it has been estimated that nearly 90% of all people will experience an incapacitating episode at some time in their lives (Gilkey et al., 2010). The Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA, 1994) identified low back pain associated with lifting as the country's number one safety challenge. Occupational factors, particularly tasks involving heavy MMH, can contribute to the onset of LBP and result in persistent low back disorder (LBD)(Ferguson, et al, 2019; Marras, 2000; Water et al., 2005). Given the high occurrence of both LBDs and MMH in the adult working population, it is estimated that LBP is perhaps the most commonly encountered work-related ailment across the globe (Fatoye, Gebrye & Odeyemi, 2019).

The lifetime prevalence of low-back pain was estimated at 84%, depending on the specific criteria used for diagnosis, affecting individuals of all age groups, including children (Trompeter, Fett and Platen, 2017). While low-back pain is not a life-threatening condition, it was the third leading cause of disability-adjusted life-years in the USA in 2010 and ranked first in terms of years lived with disability. Globally, it held the 13th position in disability-adjusted life-years for the same year (Fatoye, Gebrye and Odeyemi, 2019).

The rise in musculoskeletal disorders in many industries may be attributed to workers' high MMH demands and not adhering to safe work practices and protocols for managing ergonomic hazards. Numerous resources are available from the internet, mobile applications and other multimedia electronic recordings with information that can help guide employers and MMH workers toward safer work practices. Workers encounter a range of health-related stressors in industrial settings, such as fatigue, poor blood circulation, discomfort, and back pain, often stemming from inadequate ergonomic designs of machinery, equipment, tools and entire work systems (Rajendran et al., 2021). Suboptimal working postures may lead to reduced productivity, exacerbating health problems, musculoskeletal disorders, and physical strain. Improper work postures, including bending, lifting, twisting, pushing, and pulling, are significant contributors to the development of ergonomic problems (Rajendran et al., 2021). Less than effective training for MMH also increase risk for low back injuries (Comeau, Gonella and Lauzier, 2020).

Despite extensive research and ongoing prevention efforts, MMH continues to pose a substantial risk of occupational injuries. Data indicates that in the period between 2003 and 2008, over \$100 million annually was allocated for compensating workers in Quebec, Canada, who had suffered injuries related to manual handling (Allaire and Ricard, 2007). According to the U.S. BLS, in 2017, there were 113,620 cases of Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs) attributed to overexertion during lifting or lowering tasks in the course of work activities. The lumbar spine was the most commonly affected area, accounting for 60% of spinal injuries, with overexertion being the leading reported cause of injury, responsible for 40% of cases between 2007 and 2010 (Selvarajah et al., 2010).

1.1 Manual Material Handling Training

Raising objects from the ground is an essential task in many cases, and lifting is a recognized risk factor for experiencing LBP (Faber et al., 2009; Marras, 2000; von Arx et al., 2021; Washmut, McAfee

and Bickel, 2022). Conventional lifting techniques encompass stoop (utilizing the back for lifting), squat (involving the legs in lifting), and semi-squat (a mid-way approach between stoop and squat) (Faber et al., 2009; Kahlil, 1993; von Arx et al., 2021; Washmut, McAfee and Bickel, 2022). While many healthcare professionals consider the squat technique as the most effective, training in squat lifting does not necessarily prevent lower back pain and has been found to have high compression values that exceeded the stoop lift (Faber et al., 2009). This disparity between clinical practice and evidence-based findings has given rise to ongoing debates.

A systematic review reached the consensus that a significant portion of MMH training methods prove ineffective in reducing lower back pain or back injuries (Davis and Jorgensen, 2005; Trompeter, Fett and Platen, 2017). This lack of efficacy may be attributed to one-dimensional interventions, the absence of transferability in training, and the failure to incorporate training based on the principles of modifying health behavior (Ricci et al., 2016). Furthermore, studies often assess training effectiveness in terms of long-term outcomes, such as the reduction of musculoskeletal disorders while intermediate variables have been overlooked (Ricci et al., 2016; Robson et al., 2009; Trompeter, Fett and Platen, 2017).

One of the current challenges lies in actively engaging employees in the training process, recognizing that greater participation leads to increased effectiveness (Ricci et al., 2016; Robson et al., 2009; Trompeter, Fett, and Platen, 2017). In this context, a training method that can accentuate the active involvement of employees is self-observation. Self-observation is a valuable technique for fostering behavioral change, as it impacts self-confidence and self-awareness (Anguera et al., 2020). This research project investigated lifting techniques to assess the difference in lumbar compression using 2D L5-S1 compression. Lumbar compression has been used widely to assess risk for low back injury (Genaidy, Waly, Khalil and Hidalgo, 1993). A review of 14 studies investigating spinal compression limits for different age groups revealed variability in compression values. Risk for injury appears present in nearly all recommended limits for those engaging in various MMH tasks (Genaidy, Waly, Khalil and Hidalgo, 1993).

1.2 Research Question

What are estimates of spinal compression when workers lift materials of the same weight from ground level using different lifting methods? Is there a lower risk method to lift materials that reduces lumbar L5-S1 compression? This research seeks to shed light on the significant lower-back stresses associated with MMH commonly seen while performing usual lifting duties in many working environments. This pilot study also aims to demonstrate that amount of lumbar compression at L5-S1 is hazardous and that observed differences in L5-S1 compression is due to lifting techniques.

1.3 Old Lifting Method – Subject Background

Before performing any lifts, subjects were asked if they knew what the proper lifting technique was for picking something up off the ground. All participants stated the same or similar; approach the load with feet shoulder width apart, lift with your legs, keep your back straight and lift the load while keeping it in front of and close to their body. This is the most commonly taught technique, one which has been taught to myself at several different companies that I have worked for over the years. This method incorporates strategies like using your legs and keeping your back straight, but it leaves room for improvement.

Lifting objects in this manner keeps the weight of the load in front of the body which makes the person performing the lift put their weight on the balls of their feet, which can cause the person to lose their

balance. Keeping the load close to your body while rising also becomes difficult due to the knees getting in the way, which also makes the lifter place the load forward, increasing the chance of losing balance even more and placing greater stress on the lower back. This position also requires greater knee flexion (around 65°), which affects the legs capabilities and makes it more challenging to stand upright.

1.4 Proposed New Lifting Technique

The new method called PowerLift™ was adapted from the athletic weight lifters and is being implemented across the world is known to reduce risk associated with MMH (Copeland, 2023; Powerlift, 2023). Powerlifting incorporates techniques used by weightlifters to reduce risks and enhance performance safely. Using a wider stance allows the lifter to straddle and get closer to the load and helps reduce torso inclination and keep the feet flat on the ground thus improving stability and reducing changes of losing one's balance. This allows us to lift with our legs vertically, which allows the back to stay in alignment and transfers the weight of the load to the legs and hips. Using this method lowers the angle of knee bend to around 100° (Copeland, 2023; Powerlift, 2023).

2. METHODS

2.1 Low Back Compression Measurement

To study the compressive forces at the L5-S1 segment in the lower back, subjects of different heights and weights were recruited to perform two basic lifting tasks twice, a 35 lbs. crate from the floor using the two different techniques. Thirty-five pounds is often used and a threshold for many businesses and thought to be safer (Waters, 2007). One lift using the commonly taught method and then again, using a newer Powerlift™ technique that incorporates a wider base stance. Subjects were fitted with a 12-inch ruler for scaling dimensions and were video-recorded performing both lifts. A total of 4 subjects volunteered for a total of 8 lifts being video-recorded. Video recordings were then uploaded to a computer and still images were captured of the subjects at peak load. These photographs were then uploaded for analysis into the ErgoMaster™ software (Nexgen, 2023).

The specialized ergonomics software, ErgoMaster™ was used to predict 2D biomechanical compression at the L5-S1 spinal segment (Nexgen, 2023). Input data encompassed the location of the lifting operation, the nature of the task, the individual performing the lift, age, gender, height, weight, and the lifted load measured in English units. The subsequent set of actions involved marking specific anatomical landmarks. A dot was positioned at both ends of a 12-inch ruler for scale calibration. Following that, dots were placed on the lateral malleolus of the ankle, the lateral femoral condyle, the greater trochanter, the acromion process, the lateral epicondyle of the elbow, the second knuckle of the hand, and finally, the ear canal. The final step involves summarizing the results, which are printed and saved for later review and data extraction. Furthermore, additional force measurements were calculated, which include total compression and contributing forces at the L5-S1 segment that included shearing force, total joint reactive force, erector spinae force, and compression force in the erector spinae. These calculations are based on a 2-dimensional static model and will yield results regarding total compressive forces on the spine, shearing forces, and joint reactive force (Nexgen, 2023). To manage and organize the data, Microsoft Excel was used to create graphical presentations. (American Training Resources, 2023) Data were evaluated using Minitab™ Version 2.1. Descriptive statistics were estimated. Differences in mean scores were evaluated between old lift to new lift using the two-sample paired t-test.

3. RESULTS

Compressive forces at the L5-S1 segment of the spine revealed estimates ranging from a low of 876.25 lbs/in² to a high of 1212 lbs/in² for the old method, and a low of 691.78 lbs/in² to a high of 1046.98 lbs/in² for the new method. The old method measured a mean score of 1023.1lbs/in² (SD 76.09 lbs/in²) and the new lift was 849.09 lbs/in² (SD 82 lbs.). The new lift method demonstrated an average of 173.97 lbs/in². reduction in compression at the L5-S1. There was a significant difference found when comparing means of the old lift to new lift using the Minitab(TM) Version 21 paired t-test, p-value: < 0.00, see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Box plot with significant differences in total compression mean scores and 95% CI for Lift 1 and Lift 2

All of the lifts performed using the old method were above the action limit of NIOSH AL of 750 lbs/in², see Figure 2 whereas, the second method had two lifts below the AL, see Figure 3 and 4. Two of the subjects were still above the AL after incorporating the new method, 918.62 lbs/in² and 1046.98 lbs/in² respectively. No lifts were above the MPL. Shear forces were also evaluated using Minitab™ version 21 paired t-test for differences. Significant differences were found p-value 0.003, see Figure 6.

Compressive force due to load and compressive force due to upper body weight (UBW) increased on each subject with the new lifting method, however, every other measurement was improved with the new method. Total compressive force, total shearing force, total torque or bending moment, total joint reactive force, erector spinae force, compressive force – erector spinae, shearing force due to load, shearing force due to UBW, and shearing force – erector spinae were all reduced on all four subjects using the new lifting method, see Appendix.

Figure 2. Total L5/S1 low back compressive forces compared to NIOSH AL & MPL

Figure 3. Total L5/S1 low back compressive forces compared to NIOSH AL & MPL

Figure 4. Total shearing forces of L5/S1 compared to AL & MPL

Figure 5. Total shearing forces of L5/S1 compared to AL & MPL

Figure 6. Box plot with significant differences in total shear mean scores and 95% CI for Lift 1 and Lift 2

4. DISCUSSION

The study aimed to investigate the degree of spinal compression experienced by workers while lifting materials of the same weights from ground level to measure and evaluate whether an alternative lifting method could reduce spinal strain. The findings suggest that the Powerlift™ technique does offer a significant reduction (p-value < 0.05) for total spinal compression and shear forces in the lower back compared to the traditional approach to lifting. Our pilot study offers valuable insights into the

potential impact of lifting techniques on lower-back stresses. Prior research has found variations in compressive forces based on lifting techniques (Faber et al., 2009; von Arx et al, 2021; Washmut, McAfee and Bickel, 2022). Faber and colleagues (2021) found reduction in compressive forces using the straddle lift, which is similar to Powerlift™, compared to both stoop and squat lift methods.

The results of the current pilot study demonstrated substantial forces in the low back when lifting a 35 lbs crate. Total compressive forces associated with the commonly taught squat lift ranged from 876 lbs/in² to 1212 lbs/in², all above the NIOSH AL. Gilkey et al. (2010) examined several lifting tasks using Ergomaster™ seen on construction sites and found forces ranging from 649.0 lbs/in² to 1,938.4 lbs/in². The investigative team looked at 10 job tasks commonly performed on residential construction sites, five easy and 5 hard. The five low stress tasks were associated with bending forward without lifting to lifting small items only. Low back compression for easy tasks did not exceed 805.1 lbs/in². The five hard tasks involved lifting objects ranging from a few lbs. to 150 lbs and generated maximum compression values exceeding the NIOSH MPL (Gilkey et al., 2010). Faber and colleagues (2021) evaluated four different lifting techniques with loads ranging from 10 to 20 kgs. Researchers found compressive loads below the NIOSH MPL with loads of 20 kgs regardless of lifting technique.

The old squat-style lift reveals compressive forces above the NIOSL AL which suggest risk is present even when lifting a weight thought to be safe (Waters, 2007). The new lift style decreases compressive forces by an average of 173.97 lbs/in². Biomechanical advantages are associated with the newer lifting technique, commonly known as Powerlift™. Although the compressive forces at the L5-S1 segment still exceeded the recommended action limit in some cases, the new method showcased notable improvements in multiple measures of low back stress compared to the conventional lifting approach. The reduced total compressive force, shearing forces, joint reactive force, and erector spinae force suggest the potential benefits of adopting the Powerlift™ technique may help to mitigate the risk of back injuries among material handlers.

However, it is essential to note that while the new lifting method showed improvements in most biomechanical measures, some subjects still exceeded the NIOSH AL. We advocate for individualized training and the implementation of the Powerlift™ whenever possible. The variations among subjects emphasize the importance of personalized ergonomic interventions and training tailored to individual characteristics and capabilities.

The study's findings align with existing literature that emphasizes the association between MMH and the prevalence of low-back injury and resulting LBP. The identified risk factors, including poor lifting techniques, inadequate ergonomic designs, and suboptimal working postures, corroborate previous research highlighting the multifactorial nature of musculoskeletal disorders in occupational settings. Moreover, the study's focus on assessing the effectiveness of alternative lifting methods contributes to the ongoing discourse on the inadequacy of conventional training approaches in preventing back injuries.

5. LIMITATIONS

This pilot study has several limitations. The sample size is small and a larger sample would yield more robust findings. Loads must be smaller to allow straddling and thus the technique may not work for larger containers and awkwardly shaped loads. The Ergomaster™ software requires the accurate identity of specific landmarks to determine biomechanical angles, vectors and load moments. It is possible that minor errors may have been made in the marking exact locations of each body part. Errors

could have a differential effect that could push findings either toward or away from the null. Inferences associated with this pilot study should be made with caution.

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the investigation sheds light on the significant impact of different lifting techniques on spinal compression during MMH tasks. The study supports the potential efficacy of the Powelift™ technique in reducing biomechanical stress on the lower back compared to traditional lifting methods. However, while the newer technique displayed promising improvements, it did not universally reduce stresses below recommended safety limits (NIOSH AL) for spinal compression in all subjects. We recommend additional research will a large sample size.

None the less this team advocates for a new approach to MMH, ergonomic interventions that reduce and/or eliminate low back stresses coupled with effective training programs tailored to individual capacities and limitations (Comeau, Gonella and Lauzier, 2020). We also advocate incorporating the Powerlift™ methods for MMH. Incorporating advanced training methodologies that actively engage employees, such as behavioral-based techniques could enhance safe work practices, reduce stresses and prevent back injuries among material handlers.

Further research should explore engineering and personalized ergonomic solutions, considering factors like body morphology, strength, and work environment variability. Engineering is optimal but not universally available or applicable to all MMH tasks in all industries. Additionally, investigating the long-term effects and sustainability of implementing alternative lifting methods in diverse occupational settings will provide valuable insights into developing comprehensive strategies to safeguard MMH personnel from potential injuries and discomfort.

The findings underscore the need for continuous improvement in ergonomic practices, lifting techniques, and training protocols to address the persistent challenge of occupational LBP among manual material handlers. Ultimately, prioritizing worker safety and health through evidence-based interventions remains crucial in minimizing the burden of musculoskeletal disorders in the workplace.

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DECLARATIONS

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results.

Author's Contributions

Nick Kruzich was the student who conceived the project and worked in all phases of the study and manuscript preparation. Presented his work and graduated and now is recognized as a Graduate Safety Professional (GSP) and practicing Occupational Safety and Health. Dr. Gilkey was the Major Advisor who worked with Mr. Kruzich through all phases of the project.

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APPENDIX

2-D Static Lift**Montana Technological University**

Subject: 1
Age: 44
Sex: Male
Height: 69"
Weight: 200 lbs.
Task: Lift 1
Load: 35 lbs.

Notes:**Anthropometry:**

Shoulder-Ear: 8 in
 Forearm: 14 in
 Upper Arm: 10 in
 Trunk: 15 in
 Thigh: 15 in
 Lower Leg: 14 in

Biomechanical Angles:

Neck: 58°
 Forearm: 57°
 Upper Arm: 82°
 Trunk: 29°
 Thigh: 40°
 Leg: 63°

Biomechanical Predictions about L5/S1:

Horizontal Distance of Load: 21.8 in
 Biomechanical Angle of Trunk: 29°

Total Compressive Forces: 1076.61 lb > AL*
 Total Shearing Forces: 281.49 lb
 Total Torque or Bending Moment: 165.37 ft-lb
 Total Joint Reactive Force: 1358.10 lb
 Erector Spinae Force: 1008.16 lb
 Compressive Force due to Load: 17.00 lb
 Compressive Force due to UBW: 61.26 lb
 Compressive Force - Erector Spinae: 998.35 lb
 Shearing Force due to Load: 30.67 lb
 Shearing Force due to UBW: 110.51 lb
 Shearing Force - Erector Spinae: 140.31 lb

2-D Static Lift**Montana Technological University**

Subject: 1
Age: 44
Sex: Male
Height: 69"
Weight: 200 lbs.
Task: Lift 1
Load: 35 lbs.

Notes:**Anthropometry:**

Shoulder-Ear: 7 in
 Forearm: 14 in
 Upper Arm: 12 in
 Trunk: 16 in
 Thigh: 14 in
 Lower Leg: 17 in

Biomechanical Angles:

Neck: 55°
 Forearm: 71°
 Upper Arm: 84°
 Trunk: 39°
 Thigh: 47°
 Leg: 70°

Biomechanical Predictions about L5/S1:

Horizontal Distance of Load: 15.4 in
 Biomechanical Angle of Trunk: 39°

Total Compressive Forces: 918.62 lb > AL*

Total Shearing Forces: 240.27 lb
 Total Torque or Bending Moment: 135.34 ft-lb
 Total Joint Reactive Force: 1158.89 lb
 Erector Spinae Force: 825.06 lb
 Compressive Force due to Load: 22.07 lb
 Compressive Force due to UBW: 79.51 lb
 Compressive Force - Erector Spinae: 817.04 lb
 Shearing Force due to Load: 27.26 lb
 Shearing Force due to UBW: 98.19 lb
 Shearing Force - Erector Spinae: 114.83 lb

2-D Static Lift**Montana Technological University**

Subject: 2
Age: 18
Sex: Male
Height: 72"
Weight: 135 lbs.
Task: Lift 1
Load: 35 lbs.

Notes:**Anthropometry:**

Shoulder-Ear: 8 in
 Forearm: 16 in
 Upper Arm: 15 in
 Trunk: 18 in
 Thigh: 19 in
 Lower Leg: 17 in

Biomechanical Angles:

Neck: 67°
 Forearm: 55°
 Upper Arm: 86°
 Trunk: 26°
 Thigh: 40°
 Leg: 70°

Biomechanical Predictions about L5/S1:

Horizontal Distance of Load: 24.4 in
 Biomechanical Angle of Trunk: 26°

Total Compressive Forces: 927.04 lb > AL*

Total Shearing Forces: 230.98 lb
 Total Torque or Bending Moment: 144.83 ft-lb
 Total Joint Reactive Force: 1158.02 lb
 Erector Spinae Force: 882.90 lb
 Compressive Force due to Load: 15.37 lb
 Compressive Force due to UBW: 37.35 lb
 Compressive Force - Erector Spinae: 874.31 lb
 Shearing Force due to Load: 31.52 lb
 Shearing Force due to UBW: 76.58 lb
 Shearing Force - Erector Spinae: 122.88 lb

2-D Static Lift**Montana Technological University**

Subject: 2
Age: 18
Sex: Male
Height: 72"
Weight: 135 lbs.
Task: Lift 1
Load: 35 lbs.

Notes:**Anthropometry:**

Shoulder-Ear: 6 in
 Forearm: 13 in
 Upper Arm: 13 in
 Trunk: 18 in
 Thigh: 16 in
 Lower Leg: 18 in

Biomechanical Angles:

Neck: 54°
 Forearm: 76°
 Upper Arm: 73°
 Trunk: 33°
 Thigh: 39°
 Leg: 71°

Biomechanical Predictions about L5/S1:

Horizontal Distance of Load: 14.7 in
 Biomechanical Angle of Trunk: 33°

Total Compressive Forces: 738.99 lb
 Total Shearing Forces: 195.53 lb
 Total Torque or Bending Moment: 111.56 ft-lb
 Total Joint Reactive Force: 934.52 lb
 Erector Spinae Force: 680.10 lb
 Compressive Force due to Load: 19.10 lb
 Compressive Force due to UBW: 46.41 lb
 Compressive Force - Erector Spinae: 673.48 lb
 Shearing Force due to Load: 29.41 lb
 Shearing Force due to UBW: 71.46 lb
 Shearing Force - Erector Spinae: 94.65 lb

2-D Static Lift**Montana Technological University**

Subject: 3
Age: 18
Sex: Female
Height: 68"
Weight: 140 lbs.
Task: Lift 1
Load: 35 lbs.

Notes:**Anthropometry:**

Shoulder-Ear: 7 in
 Forearm: 15 in
 Upper Arm: 11 in
 Trunk: 16 in
 Thigh: 17 in
 Lower Leg: 16 in

Biomechanical Angles:

Neck: 54°
 Forearm: 58°
 Upper Arm: 82°
 Trunk: 35°
 Thigh: 29°
 Leg: 59°

Biomechanical Predictions about L5/S1:

Horizontal Distance of Load: 23.2 in
 Biomechanical Angle of Trunk: 35°

Total Compressive Forces: 876.25 lb > AL*

Total Shearing Forces: 214.30 lb
 Total Torque or Bending Moment: 133.42 ft-lb
 Total Joint Reactive Force: 1090.55 lb
 Erector Spinae Force: 813.37 lb
 Compressive Force due to Load: 20.12 lb
 Compressive Force due to UBW: 50.68 lb
 Compressive Force - Erector Spinae: 805.45 lb
 Shearing Force due to Load: 28.73 lb
 Shearing Force due to UBW: 72.38 lb
 Shearing Force - Erector Spinae: 113.20 lb

2-D Static Lift**Montana Technological University**

Subject: 3
Age: 18
Sex: Female
Height: 68"
Weight: 140 lbs.
Task: Lift 1
Load: 35 lbs.

Notes:**Anthropometry:**

Shoulder-Ear: 6 in
 Forearm: 13 in
 Upper Arm: 12 in
 Trunk: 16 in
 Thigh: 15 in
 Lower Leg: 17 in

Biomechanical Angles:

Neck: 58°
 Forearm: 74°
 Upper Arm: 88°
 Trunk: 47°
 Thigh: 36°
 Leg: 68°

Biomechanical Predictions about L5/S1:

Horizontal Distance of Load: 15.4 in
 Biomechanical Angle of Trunk: 47°

Total Compressive Forces: 691.78 lb
 Total Shearing Forces: 168.71 lb
 Total Torque or Bending Moment: 99.64 ft-lb
 Total Joint Reactive Force: 860.49 lb
 Erector Spinae Force: 607.42 lb
 Compressive Force due to Load: 25.65 lb
 Compressive Force due to UBW: 64.62 lb
 Compressive Force - Erector Spinae: 601.51 lb
 Shearing Force due to Load: 23.92 lb
 Shearing Force due to UBW: 60.26 lb
 Shearing Force - Erector Spinae: 84.54 lb

2-D Static Lift**Montana Technological University**

Subject: 4
Age: 18
Sex: Male
Height: 72"
Weight: 210 lbs.
Task: Lift 1
Load: 35 lbs.

Notes:**Anthropometry:**

Shoulder-Ear: 11 in
 Forearm: 15 in
 Upper Arm: 14 in
 Trunk: 21 in
 Thigh: 18 in
 Lower Leg: 17 in

Biomechanical Angles:

Neck: 79°
 Forearm: 62°
 Upper Arm: 88°
 Trunk: 29°
 Thigh: 35°
 Leg: 72°

Biomechanical Predictions about L5/S1:

Horizontal Distance of Load: 26.0 in
 Biomechanical Angle of Trunk: 29°

Total Compressive Forces: 1212.35 lb > AL*
 Total Shearing Forces: 305.65 lb
 Total Torque or Bending Moment: 187.35 ft-lb
 Total Joint Reactive Force: 1518.00 lb
 Erector Spinae Force: 1142.16 lb
 Compressive Force due to Load: 17.00 lb
 Compressive Force due to UBW: 64.31 lb
 Compressive Force - Erector Spinae: 1131.04 lb
 Shearing Force due to Load: 30.67 lb
 Shearing Force due to UBW: 116.01 lb
 Shearing Force - Erector Spinae: 158.96 lb

2-D Static Lift**Montana Technological University**

Subject: 4
Age: 18
Sex: Male
Height: 72"
Weight: 210 lbs.
Task: Lift 1
Load: 35 lbs.

Notes:**Anthropometry:**

Shoulder-Ear: 11 in
 Forearm: 14 in
 Upper Arm: 18 in
 Trunk: 24 in
 Thigh: 19 in
 Lower Leg: 20 in

Biomechanical Angles:

Neck: 87°
 Forearm: 79°
 Upper Arm: 70°
 Trunk: 31°
 Thigh: 44°
 Leg: 68°

Biomechanical Predictions about L5/S1:

Horizontal Distance of Load: 17.1 in
 Biomechanical Angle of Trunk: 31°

Total Compressive Forces: 1046.98 lb > AL*

Total Shearing Forces: 278.76 lb
 Total Torque or Bending Moment: 159.12 ft-lb
 Total Joint Reactive Force: 1325.75 lb
 Erector Spinae Force: 970.04 lb
 Compressive Force due to Load: 18.06 lb
 Compressive Force due to UBW: 68.32 lb
 Compressive Force - Erector Spinae: 960.60 lb
 Shearing Force due to Load: 30.06 lb
 Shearing Force due to UBW: 113.70 lb
 Shearing Force - Erector Spinae: 135.00 lb

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

ACTION LIMIT (AL):

A load weight above which musculoskeletal injury incidence and severity rates increase moderately. It is defined by the following criteria:

- Compressive forces acting on the L5/S1 spinal disc are 3425 N (770 lb) or greater.
- Twenty-five percent of the female workers and one percent of the male workers do not have the muscle strengths to be capable of performing the work.
- Metabolic rates would exceed 3.5 Kcal/minute (when integrated over an eight-hour day).
- Lumbosacral torque equal to or greater than 163 N-m (120 ft-lb) is considered hazardous to all but the healthiest of workers, as proposed by OSHA.

BIOMECHANICS:

The application of mechanics to the living human body.

COMPRESSION:

Occurs when equal and opposite loads are applied toward the surface of the vertebrae.

MAXIMUM PERMISSIBLE LIMIT (MPL):

A load weight at which musculoskeletal injury rates and severity rates have been shown to increase significantly. It is defined by the following criteria:

- Compressive forces acting on the L5/S1 spinal disc are 6361 N (1430 lb) or greater.
- Seventy-five percent of the men and ninety-percent of the women do not have the muscle strengths to be capable of performing the work.
- Metabolic rates in excess of 5.0 Kcal/minute (when integrated over an eight-hour day).

MUSCULOSKELETAL:

Refers to a system that consists of the peripheral parts of the motor system and comprises muscle and the connective tissue elements that form the skeleton.

SHEAR:

Occurs when a force is applied parallel to the surface of the vertebrae.

TORQUE:

or moment of a force, is the product of a force times the perpendicular distance from its line of action to the axis of motion (or potential motion). Force x Distance.

UPPER BODY WEIGHT (UBW):

Represents approximately 65% of the force exerted by the total body weight.

Subject #1	1	Old Method	New Method	Difference
Male	Total Compressive Forces (lbs):	1076.61	918.62	157.99
69	Total Shearing Forces (lbs):	281.49	240.27	41.22
200	Total Torque or Bending Moment (ft-lb):	165.37	135.34	30.03
	Total Joint Reactive Force (lbs):	1358.1	1158.89	199.21
	Erector Spinae Force (lbs):	1008.16	825.06	183.1
	Compressive Force due to Load (lbs):	17	22.07	-5.07
	Compressive Force due to UBW (lbs):	61.26	79.51	-18.25
	Compressive Force - Erector Spinae	998.35	817.04	181.31
	Shearing Force due to Load (lbs):	30.67	27.26	3.41
	Shearing Force due to UBW (lbs):	110.51	98.19	12.32
	Shearing Force - Erector Spinae (lbs)	140.31	114.83	25.48
Subject #2	2			
Male	Total Compressive Forces (lbs):	927.04	738.99	188.05
72	Total Shearing Forces (lbs):	230.98	195.53	35.45
135	Total Torque or Bending Moment (ft-lb):	144.83	111.56	33.27
	Total Joint Reactive Force (lbs):	1158.02	934.52	223.5
	Erector Spinae Force (lbs):	882.9	680.1	202.8
	Compressive Force due to Load (lbs):	15.37	19.1	-3.73
	Compressive Force due to UBW (lbs):	37.35	46.41	-9.06
	Compressive Force - Erector Spinae	874.31	673.48	200.83
	Shearing Force due to Load (lbs):	31.52	29.41	2.11
	Shearing Force due to UBW (lbs):	76.58	71.46	5.12
	Shearing Force - Erector Spinae (lbs)	122.88	94.65	28.23
Subject #3	3			
Female	Total Compressive Forces (lbs):	876.25	691.78	184.47
68	Total Shearing Forces (lbs):	214.3	168.71	45.59
140	Total Torque or Bending Moment (ft-lb):	133.42	99.64	33.78
	Total Joint Reactive Force (lbs):	1090.55	860.49	230.06
	Erector Spinae Force (lbs):	813.37	607.42	205.95
	Compressive Force due to Load (lbs):	20.12	25.65	-5.53
	Compressive Force due to UBW (lbs):	50.68	64.62	-13.94
	Compressive Force - Erector Spinae	805.45	601.51	203.94
	Shearing Force due to Load (lbs):	28.73	23.92	4.81
	Shearing Force due to UBW (lbs):	72.38	60.26	12.12
	Shearing Force - Erector Spinae (lbs)	113.2	84.54	28.66
Subject #4	4			
Male	Total Compressive Forces (lbs):	1212.35	1046.98	165.37
72	Total Shearing Forces (lbs):	305.65	278.76	26.89
210	Total Torque or Bending Moment (ft-lb):	187.35	159.12	28.23
	Total Joint Reactive Force (lbs):	1518	1325.75	192.25
	Erector Spinae Force (lbs):	1142.16	970.04	172.12
	Compressive Force due to Load (lbs):	17	18.06	-1.06
	Compressive Force due to UBW (lbs):	64.31	68.32	-4.009999999999999
	Compressive Force - Erector Spinae	1131.04	960.6	170.44
	Shearing Force due to Load (lbs):	30.67	30.06	0.6100000000000003
	Shearing Force due to UBW (lbs):	116.01	113.7	2.31
	Shearing Force - Erector Spinae (lbs)	158.96	135	23.96
Averages	Avg. Total Compressive Forces	1023.0625	849.0925	173.97
	Avg. Total Shearing Forces:	411.0965	346.4725	64.62399999999999
	Avg. Total Torque or Bending Moment	344.1881667	283.5375	60.65066666666667
	Avg. Total Joint Reactive Force:	986.1453095	1069.9125	-83.7671904761904
	Avg. Erector Spinae Force:	961.6475	703.954375	257.693125
	Avg. Compressive Force due to Load	17.3725	21.22	-3.8475
	Avg. Compressive Force due to UBW	53.4	64.715	-11.315
	Avg. Compressive Force - Erector Sp	952.2875	763.1575	189.13
	Avg. Shearing Force due to Load:	30.3975	27.6625	2.735
	Avg. Shearing Force due to UBW:	93.87	85.9025	7.967500000000002
	Avg. Shearing Force - Erector Spinae	386.3441054	107.255	279.089105442177

The data from the above table are displayed in the figures below.

MAIN AUTHOR

Nick Kruzich is a driven professional who recently graduated with a Bachelor of Science in Occupational Safety and Health from Montana Technological University. Currently serving as an EHS Engineer for The Whiting-Turner Contracting Company, Nick applies his knowledge and expertise to oversee Environmental, Health, and Safety protocols within the company. With a strong foundation in occupational safety principles, Nick works diligently to implement and enforce comprehensive safety measures, contributing significantly to the well-being of employees and the success of ongoing projects. His dedication to promoting a culture of safety underscores his passion for creating workplaces where individuals can thrive without compromising their health and well-being.

